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Formation of a matrix of financial and credit benefits in the system of state support of strategic priorities of innovative development of the country

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the solution of the problem of creation of uniform methodical base of definition of structure and rationing of size of financial - credit privileges in system of economic stimulation of realization of strategic priorities of innovative development of the country. For the approved state strategic directions of innovative development taking into account the degree of their relative importance in the general system of priorities within the chosen time horizon and the provided scales of their indirect government support the procedure of selection of the corresponding list of financial and credit privileges is formed taking into account budgetary restrictions. The proposed algorithm for the formation of the matrix of benefits prevents the dispersion of benefits between many priority areas in small amounts and is focused on creating an effective system of state incentives for innovation and technological activity. An organic combination of heuristic and formal methods of decision-making during the implementation of the developed procedure in practice will counteract departmental interests and subjectivity in choosing the composition and rationing of financial and credit benefits and will redistribute resources in favor of those areas that can provide positive technological change. national economy.

1 Introduction

The determining factor in the development of the state in the modern world is economic growth as a result of a continuous process of updating knowledge and technology and active implementation of innovations in economic practice. Timely revision of priority areas of science and technology in order to bring them closer to the areas identified in developed countries, based on modern global technological trends is considered one of the defining conditions for building an innovative economy in Ukraine with developed entrepreneurship, innovation and high productivity [1]. An important component of ensuring the effective implementation of the strategy of innovative development of national systems is the active indirect financial support from the state of the declared priorities. Successful solution of the problem of optimizing the procedure of forming a system of economic incentives and determining the scope of providing appropriate benefits to each of the priority areas of innovative development of the country solves the problem of attracting hidden potential of the private sector and foreign investment in the process of financing innovation.

2 Presenting main material

The practice of state regulation of the sphere of innovation activity of the advanced countries of the world community testifies to the expansion of the sphere of application of economic stimulants. Constant adaptation of the system of benefits and preferences within the tax, customs, depreciation, credit, pricing policy to new guidelines of scientific and technological development and changes in economic, political, social life of the state, intensifies the inflow of private investment in scientific and technical research and development and provides modernization and renewal of production on the basis of new equipment and technology.

Such domestic scientists as Yu. M. Bazhal, V. M. Heyets, AI Danylenko, OI Zhilinska, OL Evmeshkina, EM Libanova, MO Kizim, IV Odotyuk, NE Teryoshkina, ZV Yurinetz [2-7] made a significant contribution to the study of the processes of state regulation of innovative development of the national economy. However, in modern science the problem of linking the scale of indirect state support for the strategic direction of innovation with the level of its relative priority is not sufficiently disclosed, even in theoretical terms.

The basic concept of state indirect stimulation of innovation and technological activity provides for the provision of a specific set of financial and credit benefits and preferences to a strictly limited list of activities and leading sectors of the economy that can ensure positive technological change in the country. This requires parity of the intentions of legislators, government agencies and budgetary capabilities of the country in order to consolidate the available resources for the implementation of priority areas of innovation development. Economic incentives do not limit the actions of economic entities in determining their own goals and the choice of means of their implementation, increase the incentives to innovate in terms of economic benefits for the results achieved, which is fully consistent with the

20 November 2020

principles of market regulation. Financial and credit benefits reduce the costs of private sector companies for research and development. This provides an opportunity to further appropriate a certain share of benefits and meet existing needs at a higher level. At the same time, the benefits guaranteed by economic incentives are encouraging and impose economic responsibility for the quality of activities and the level of its effectiveness.

Unfortunately, during the years of independence in Ukraine at the state level no effective mechanism for economic stimulation of innovation has been created.

As you know, the economic behavior of the subject is determined not only by active needs, but is also a function of its perception and expectations associated with a particular situation, and the possible consequences of their chosen type of behavior. Note that this fact has been ignored for a long time in Ukraine in the formation of a system of economic incentives for innovation. This leads to such negative phenomena as the formation of a system of benefits that does not meet the resource capabilities of economic entities, the constant change of conditions for the use of benefits provided by the state, up to complete rejection, lack of clear legal support for their implementation. Probably, in such a situation the positive effect of financial and credit regulators on the pace of scientific and technological progress is sharply reduced. The instability of the system of state economic stimulation of innovation, its inadequacy to the characteristics of the external environment of economic entities and their internal potential, other things being equal, prevents the creation of a favorable atmosphere for effective work of investors, researchers, producers and consumers of scientific and technical products. As a result, entities operating in this field or showing interest in it do not see prospects for achieving positive results from the implementation of scientific, technical and innovative measures. As a result, they form negative expectations about the feasibility of this activity, which, in turn, becomes a serious obstacle to the formation of an innovative type of behavior of economic agents.

Meanwhile, public administration through economic interest should provide the opportunity to meet different groups of needs of the subject of business relations through such a course of action that would contribute to the conditions of economic growth and the solution of problems facing the national economy.

The incentive, which is considered as a state-guaranteed reward for the results of innovative activities, should provide the subject with a set of benefits that have real value for him, and the level of economic activity in a given system of incentives depends on expectations that between efforts spent to achieve the result, and the resulting set of benefits there is a stable relationship, and the benefits are adequate to the efforts made. By directing the efforts of economic agents to achieve a specific result, the system of incentives, in our opinion, should create for them a set of external benefits by giving them a temporary right of priority access to limited resources and preferential treatment of economic activity. At the same time, achieving the required level of efficiency in the implementation of a particular activity has a positive effect on the internal potential of the business entity and provides it with a number of internal benefits - the ability to increase qualitative and quantitative parameters of its activities, strengthening resource and technical maneuvering. strengthening of own property base, creation of steady competitive advantages, formation of positive business image, etc.

The higher the degree of correspondence between the set of benefits actually provided by the state in practice from the implementation of the incentive measure and the expectations of the economic entity formed in relation to it, the greater the value of this complex and, consequently, the level of relative satisfaction. This assessment determines the degree of effectiveness of the system of economic incentives used by the state, affects the nature of the economic agent's perception of future situations, necessitates the preservation or adjustment of his previously chosen line of business behavior.

The system of economic stimulation of scientific, technical and innovative activity formed at the state level should, first of all, take into account and coordinate the interests of different groups of economic agents covered by the relations of production, exchange, distribution and consumption in this sphere. The process of finding, creating, producing and implementing innovations will be continuous and dynamic, if, other things being equal, each of its participants, developing and strengthening its own activities, can take advantage of state-guaranteed external benefits, while the results achieved are the basis for further progressive development of this process and meeting both the private interests of its partners and public needs. This is possible only in the situation when the system of state stimulation of scientific, technical and innovative activities will create a motivational field that encourages business entities to reconcile their competing interests in the course of its implementation. Under such conditions, the system of state economic incentives will guide businesses not only to participate in the implementation of scientific, technical and innovative activities, but, above all, to obtain certain end results.

However, it should be borne in mind that each business entity is based on the principle of economic feasibility, hoping to obtain both external and internal benefits, which will be fully realized only in the presence of full demand for positive results of scientific and technical activities. Thus under full-fledged we will understand such level of demand at which the organization realizes the purposes planned during planning, achieving desirable results. Therefore, the system of indirect support of subjects in the field of science and technology should contribute to the formation and maintenance of such demand for the results of innovation.

Thus, economic incentives as the most important component of state innovation policy should become a system of state-guaranteed unstable competitive advantages, which gives economic entities a temporary priority right to pursue their own economic interests and encourages them to proactively coordinate these competing interests to create, develop,

20 November 2020

disseminate and the application of the results of scientific, technical and innovative activities, which is aimed at forming and maintaining a full demand for them.

The possibility of temporary operation within the most favorable tax climate, obtaining the right of priority access to limited material resources, preferential long-term loans are duplicated, unstable competitive advantages, which are guaranteed by the state to economic entities that accumulate and direct their own strategic resources for implementation. Prospects for obtaining these unstable competitive advantages over a period of time under the conditions proposed by the state will contribute to the formation of positive expectations of economic entities regarding the possibility of further gaining and maintaining high competitive advantages, ie creating a number of internal benefits: ability to continuous self-improvement and material development. -technical base of the enterprise on the basis of attraction of new technics, advanced technologies, development of goods-novelty, updating and expansion of assortment of production, formation of the highly skilled personnel focused on use of the newest technologies in various spheres of activity and, as a result, satisfaction of needs of clientele at higher quality level. than other manufacturers. At the same time, an important factor that helps to form an effective system of state economic stimulation of innovation is the real provision in practice of economic entities of all those unstable competitive advantages that were previously declared by the state. Otherwise, the acquisition of negative experience by economic entities from the implementation of innovation activities due to breach of state obligations will further lead to the formation of negative expectations about the feasibility of activities in this area and will only hinder the formation of innovative behavior in the latter. However, the system of state economic stimulation of innovation should contribute to the transformation of short-term interest of the economic entity in the implementation of scientific and technical measures in a stable dominant interest in the development and implementation of innovations as a means of reproducing its economic condition and a source of competitive advantage. This requires that the state's economic regulators in practice meet the expectations of economic entities and at the same time provide both increasing the interest of economic agents in the accumulation and placement of various investment resources in the field of innovation, long-term lending to upgrade production and technical base of enterprises and development of new species. products, and strengthening the interest of enterprises and organizations in attracting and using the resources provided to achieve the objectives.

It should be borne in mind that within the framework of each of the priority areas approved at the state level, specific activities differ significantly in terms of the level of the already existing reserve, therefore, they require different time and resource costs during implementation. In addition, individual activities can be simultaneously included in several priority areas of innovation, and, therefore, be considered as more significant from the standpoint of the successful implementation of the adopted strategy. Therefore, in addition to choosing priority areas, it is necessary to assess the relative priority of the measures included in their composition, to rank them based on the analysis of the results obtained, on the basis of which, to determine the amount of state support and normalize the amount of financial and credit benefits provided for each measure taken. Apparently, the solution of the stated problem of organic examination of expert and formal methods of solving the problem has been successfully solved.

In practice, the implementation of one or another priority area of innovation is a set of separate works of a certain duration, which can be performed both sequentially one after the other and in parallel. Thus, the technology for the practical implementation of each direction, and the entire system of priority areas as a whole, can be presented in the form of a network schedule, the elements of which are long-term work, reflecting all the nuances of the implementation of the direction. The general scheme of the algorithm for forming a unified network schedule for the implementation of priority areas of innovation is shown in Fig. 1.

Further, on the basis of the standard procedure for solving the problem of network modeling, ranking according to the level of priority of works (activities) of the network schedule for the implementation of the basic directions of innovation is carried out. Each work has a corresponding numerical value of the total priority, calculated taking into account the opinion and preferences of a group of experts. Therefore, taking any two works of the network schedule and calculating the ratio of the values of their relative priority, it is possible, taking into account the obtained proportion, to conclude which of the indicated works is of higher priority.

Based on the existing budgetary constraints for the planned period of time, the total amount of funds allocated for the state economic stimulation of innovative activity, each work of the network schedule is provided with indirect state support on a scale corresponding to the proportions of the obtained values of the total priorities of these works.

20 November 2020

Figure: 1 - General scheme of the algorithm for the formation of a unified network schedule of work on implementation state priorities in the field of innovation

Based on the state-approved basic list of strategic directions of innovative development of the country n , the established level of their relative priority p_i , $i = 1, n$ within the chosen time horizon and the envisaged scale of their

20 November 2020

indirect government support, we will form a procedure for selecting the appropriate list of financial and credit benefits for each of the identified areas.

At the first stage of this procedure, a group of experts (representatives of government institutions responsible for strategic decision-making, financiers, taxpayers, business leaders, leading scientists, etc.) identify using standard heuristic decision-making methods m possible types of financial and credit benefits and determine for each of them two values:

~ $V_j, j = 1, m$ - the maximum amount of use of benefits within the selected time horizon;

~ $V_{j0}, j = 1, m$ - the maximum amount of benefits to a particular priority area n ;

Note that for those benefits in which the upper limit of the scope of their application is not limited, we consider the value of V_j as large as possible.

As a result of realization of the first stage at an exit we have n directions of innovative development of the country and m corresponding to them possible kinds of financial - credit privileges.

The second stage of the procedure is also heuristic - a group of experts determines a set of numerical values of z_{ij} - the relative priority of the i -th scientific - technical or innovative direction for the use of the j -th benefit.

These numerical values are determined on an arbitrary scale, but for further formal calculations it is convenient to use the interval $(0, 1)$.

We emphasize that the implementation of the two considered stages takes place according to the standard multi-step procedure of the method of expert evaluations.

The third stage of the procedure is the formation of a matrix of benefits.

Enter the value:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{P_i * Z_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^n P_i * Z_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

From relation (1) it follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n P_{ij} = 1 \quad (2)$$

Therefore, we will call the value of P_{ij} - the normalized relative priority of the i -th innovation direction for the j -th privilege, which characterizes the possible degree of its use in this direction.

Note that the calculations of formula (1) directly use the values of the established level of relative priority of the directions of innovative development of the country $p_i, i = 1, n$ within the selected time horizon.

After calculating the values of P_{ij} , we can proceed to the direct calculation of the initial values of each j -th benefit for each i -th direction V_{ij} by the formula:

$$V_{ij} = P_{ij} * V_j \quad (3)$$

Note that the selected values of P_{ij} meet the mandatory condition:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n P_{ij} * V_{ij} = V_j * \sum_{i=1}^n P_{ij} = V_j \quad (4)$$

That is, the sum of the volumes of each privilege distributed in all priority areas is equal to the maximum volume of its use for a given period of time.

Thus, we have a matrix $V = (V_{ij})$ of dimension $n \times m$, which we will call the matrix of benefits. Note that due to the application of formal methods in step 3 of this procedure there is no guarantee that for all elements of the matrix of benefits for each i - the priority direction and for each j -th preference is the relationship $V_{ij} \geq V_{j0}, i = 1, n; j = 1, m$.

As a result, benefits may be scattered among many priority areas in small amounts, which will prevent the formation of an effective system of state incentives for innovation and technological activity.

It is possible to avoid this problem in step 4 of the proposed procedure by applying step-by-step Algorithm 1:

Step 1. $j = 0$. The initial step of the algorithm.

Step 2. $j = j + 1$. We turn to the consideration of the next type of benefits.

Step 3. Check the relationship $j > m$.

If the relation is fulfilled, then the transition to the end of this algorithm, if it is not fulfilled, then go to step 4.

Step 4. $i = 0$. The initial step is to search for all strategic priorities.

Step 5. $i = i + 1$. We turn to the consideration of the next priority area.

Step 6. $w = V_{j0}$, where w is the minimum amount of use of the j -th privilege.

Step 7. Check the relationship $0 < V_{ij} < w$.

20 November 2020

If the ratio is not met, ie either for this priority area, this benefit is not allocated at all ($V_{ij} = 0$), or allocated in amounts that do not reach the minimum, then go to step 10.

Otherwise, go to step 8.

Step 8. $l = i$, where l is the number of the priority area for which the minimum amount of the j -th privilege is provided.

Step 9. $w = V_{ij}$.

Step 10. Check the fulfillment of the relation $i < n$.

If the relation is fulfilled, we return to step 5 to consider the next direction.

If the ratio is not fulfilled, ie the consideration of all n priority areas in relation to the j -th privilege is completed, then we proceed to step 11.

Step 11. Check the performance of the relation $w < V_{j0}$.

If the ratio is met, it is necessary to adjust the amount of benefits for this area and go to step 12.

If the ratio is not met, then go to step 2 to consider the next benefit.

Step 12. Adjusting the amount of benefits of the j -th variety for the i -th priority area.

At this stage of Algorithm 1 we have the number l of the priority area, which allocated the minimum amount of benefits of the j -th variety - the value of w . In this case, $0 < w < V_{j0}$.

The essence of adjusting the volume of the j -th privilege for this i -th priority is to redistribute the volume w of the privilege between all selected promising areas in proportion to their priority, calculated according to relation (1), according to the following formula in accordance with (3) :

$$V_{ij} = P_{ij} * V_j + P_{ij} * V_{lj} = P_{ij} (V_j + V_{lj}) \quad (5)$$

Note that the total amount of additional benefits in all priority areas, according to formula (2), satisfies relation (6):

$$\sum_{i=1}^n P_{ij} * V_{ij} = V_{lj} \sum_{i=1}^n P_{ij} = V_{lj} = w \quad (6)$$

Thus, the amount of benefits of the j -th variety for the most important areas is increased by the value of w in proportion to the value of their relative priority.

Step 13. $V_{lj} = 0$.

Since it is necessary to perform relation (4), increasing the total amount of the j -th privilege for the priority direction by the value of $w = V_{lj}$, it is necessary to simultaneously reduce its volume by the same value in the direction of l for which $w < V_{j0}$ and does not play any role in its implementation .

We carry out transition to a stage 4.

The implementation of stage 4 has a fully formalized character and practically deprives subjectivism of decision-making on the distribution of funds, which are aimed at the goals of state economic stimulation of innovation.

After the end of stage 4, there are no such values of V_{ij} that the ratio $V_{ij} < V_{j0}$ is fulfilled, ie the optimization of the matrix of benefits by the criterion of minimizing their dispersion in all priority areas. Thus in the final variant each element V_{ij} of a matrix of privileges defines the maximum possible volume of the j -th privilege for the given i -th direction taking into account all existing restrictions.

We emphasize that steps 3 and 4 of this procedure are fully formalized, so they can be easily and quickly implemented using computer technology in an interactive mode by implementing Algorithm 2:

Step 1. Implementation of the actions of stage 1 - heuristic methods of management decisions.

Step 2. Implementation of the actions of stage 2 - heuristic methods of management decisions.

Step 3. Implementation of actions of stage 3 and stage 4 - formal methods of making managerial decisions.

Step 4. Analysis of the elements of the formed matrix of benefits.

Step 5. Experts check the satisfaction of the values of the matrix of benefits.

If the values are satisfactory, then the end of the algorithm, otherwise - go to step 6.

Step 6. Checking the satisfaction of the composition of benefits based on the analysis of the matrix of benefits.

If the system of benefits is acceptable - go to step 2, otherwise - go to step 1.

20 November 2020

Note that the implementation of this algorithm is very effective given the formal mathematical support and the possibility of using heuristic management decisions in the Internet - conference mode.

3 Conclusions from the conducted research

Thus, based on the implementation of the proposed methodology, we obtain for each strategic direction of innovative development of the state taking into account the level of its relative priority within the specified time horizon, a specific list of state-guaranteed financial and credit benefits as much as possible, taking into account all existing budget constraints.

An organic combination of heuristic and formal decision-making methods during the implementation of the developed procedure in practice will allow to oppose departmental interests and subjectivism in the choice of composition and rationing of financial and credit benefits, which will increase the efficiency of state economic stimulation of innovation and redistribution of resources. areas of activity that should ensure positive technological changes in the national economy. Under this approach, the mechanism of state economic stimulation of innovative development can be organically integrated into the system of market relations and implemented on the basis of coordinated application of a set of incentive benefits of purely targeted nature, which meet current budget constraints, are enshrined in law and operate automatically.

It should be noted that the acceleration and globalization of scientific and technical processes necessitate the constant enrichment of the system of state economic regulators and ensure its maximum compliance with the expectations of economic agents in order to increase their interest in accumulating and allocating various resources in science and technology and innovation. outlines the directions of further research on this topic.

References

1. Strategiya rozvy`tku sfery` innovacijnoyi diyal`nosti na period do 2030 roku [Elektronny`j resurs]. – Rezhy`m dostupu: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/526-2019-r>
2. Bazhal Yu. M. Rozvy`tok innovacijnoyi diyal`nosti u znannyevomu try`kutny`ku "derzhava – universy`tety` – promy`slovist`" / Yu. M. Bazhal // Ekonomika i prognozuvannya. - 2015. - # 1. - S. 76-88. - Rezhy`m dostupu: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/econprog_2015_1_8.
3. Innovacijna Ukrajina 2020 : nacional`na dopovid` / za zag. red.V.M. Gejcyja ta in. ; NAN Ukrainy`. – K., 2015. – 336 s.
4. Ukrajina 2030: Doktry`na zbalansovanogo rozvy`tku. Vy`dannya druge. – L`viv: Kal`variya, 2017. – 164 s.
5. Evmeshky`na E. L. Formy`rovany`e metodov gosudarstvennogo strategy`cheskogo plany`rovany`ya / E. L. Evmeshky`na // Legea Si Viata (Zakon y` zhy`zn`) : mezhdunar. nauch.-prakt. pravovoj zhurnal. – 2017. – # 1/2. – S. 70-73.
6. Ter`oshkina N. Ye. Innovacijna strategiya v sy`stemi upravlinnya nacional`noyu ekonomikoyu / N. Ye. Ter`oshkina // Markety`ng i menedzhment innovacij. – 2014. – # 2. – S. 151-161.
7. Yury`necz` Z. V. Inozemny`j dosvid formuvannya nacional`ny`x innovacijny`x sy`stem ta jogo realiyi v Ukraini / Z. V. Yury`necz` // Visny`k L`vivs`kogo universy`tetu. Seriya ekonomichna. – 2014. – Vy`pusk 51. – S. 230 – 236.